

1 **Composition of an Xist RNP complex that functions to promote clonal fitness: SAFB.**

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6 We recently described Xist induction (and in some cases its silencing), as a recurrent transcriptional event
7 associated with p53-deficient backgrounds, and demonstrated Xist activation is directly controlled by loss
8 of tumor suppressor (p53 or Rb) function. Xist expression is high soon after the onset of transformation; in
9 some cancer types, like breast cancer, its expression remains high while in others its expression levels
10 subside but remain detectable at clinical presentation of solid tumors. Xist activation is functionally
11 relevant, as it influences clonal selection early in disease evidenced by its control of subtype selection in
12 human breast cancer and human lung cancer. We used proteomic and transcriptomic techniques to
13 identify the existence of a putative Xist RNP complex in cancer whose composition varies based on
14 context and expression but whose major function appears to be modulation of interleukin enhancer factors
15 ILF2/3 and likely possesses epigenetic silencing and activation functions reminiscent of its function in
16 development but with a wider range of transcriptional targets. SAFB was a bona fide protein-interaction
17 partner of the non-coding RNA Xist and expression of Xist controlled or was tightly co-regulated with
18 SAFB or recently described Xist RNP complex members in multiple settings. We describe here the
19 identification of a fourth component of the Xist RNP complex, *SAFB*.

Results

We previously found expression of the non-coding RNA that controls X-inactivation during development in mammalian females, Xist, among the largest transcriptional differences when comparing p53-sufficient and p53-deficient breast cancer cell lines (1). We hypothesized the existence of an Xist-containing RNP complex that drives tumor progression, recurrence and metastasis in humans with breast cancer. We recently utilized published mass spectrometric data to deconvolute the composition of this hypothetical complex, revealing the RNA-binding protein KHDRBS1 was a *bona fide* protein interaction partner of Xist (Chart 1). Discovery research indicated that a separate molecule, scaffold attachment factor B (encoded by SAFB) might also function in an Xist RNP complex during transformation and in cancer. We found using proteomic methods, similar to KHDRBS1, that SAFB was a *bona fide* protein interaction partner of Xist (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Mass spectrometry in Xist-expressing stem cells reveals SAFB is an Xist interacting protein.

Chu and Chang, Cell, 2015: KHDRBS1

	<u>Epiblast stem cells</u>	<u>Trophoblast stem cells</u>
<u>Peptide count</u>	26	26
	<u>Epiblast stem cells (-)</u>	<u>Trophoblast stem cells (-)</u>
<u>Peptide count</u>	0	0

SAFB peptides were isolated using Xist as bait, demonstrating protein-RNA interaction between SAFB protein and the Xist non-coding RNA transcript (**Figure 1**).

Figure 2: Transgenic expression of Xist in human fibroblasts results in silencing of SAFB.

GSE68109

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (day 1; no doxycycline [DOX])

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

Transgenic expression of Xist in human cells (transformed fibroblasts) resulted in near complete silencing of SAFB. Silencing of SAFB following forced expression of Xist indicated control of an Xist complex component by Xist expression levels.

ID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
6294	3.58E-15	0.0991	7.87	7.80E-01	4370.82	SAFB	165/18377	99.1

We next measured total transcription in human embryonic stem cells, clonally selected based on expression of Xist, comparing hES clones positive for Xist expression to that of hES clones negative for Xist expression (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Expression in Xist in human embryonic stem cells at the clonal level was associated with expression (significant transcriptional induction) of SAFB.

GSE87321

n=2 Xist-negative human embryonic stem cell (hES) clones

n=2 Xist-positive human embryonic stem cell clones

ID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
6294	1.54E-03	0.167	-3.1664061	-0.5281928	5726.77	SAFB	1273/17710	92.8

Xist expression in human embryonic stem cells was clearly associated with induction of SAFB, together with observations from forced Xist expression in transformed fibroblasts indicating dual

1 repressive and supportive control of SAFB expression by the SAFB-interacting ncRNA Xist (**Figure 3**).

2
3 We recently demonstrated that the putative Xist RNP complex consisted of, at least, Xist and
4 KHDRBS1 or a KH-domain-containing family members (KHDRBS2 or KHDRBS3), with a major function of
5 the Xist RNP complex being ILF2/3-mediated transcriptional modulation at an undisclosed number of
6 genomic loci whose targeting mechanism remained unclear. We found using advanced transcriptional
7 co-regulation methods that among the transcripts in the human genome whose expression was most
8 closely co-regulated with SAFB was *ILF3*, who proteomic methods also demonstrated was an
9 Xist-interacting protein, *KHDRBS1*, *BAZ1B*, as well as the known Xist-interacting partner and
10 Xist-localizing factor *SPEN* (**Figure 4**).

11 **Figure 4:** ILF3, KHDRBS1, SPEN and BAZ1B are among the genes most closely co-regulated with SAFB
12 across the entire human transcriptome.

13 Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
SAFB	6294	-3.2	0.0036	scaffold attachment factor B		

14 Coexpressed genes: (out of 17,858 total transcripts)

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	%Co-reg
2	ILF3	3609	2.6508	0.0046	99.99
3	FUS	2521	2.645	0.0001	99.98
100	KHDRBS1	10657	1.8792	0.0196	99.4
102	SPEN	23013	1.8717	0.0136	99.4
183	BAZ1B	9031	1.6975	0.0153	99.0

15 Discussion

16 We provided evidence here demonstrating *SAFB* interacts with Xist in a putative Xist RNP complex
17 functioning in transformation and cancer in humans, together with *KHDRBS1* and *ILF3*. We recently
18 discovered and described additional components of the Xist RNP complex, which we have argued exists
19 in multiple variant forms based primarily on subunit composition but also based on genomic target
20 choice, including *BAZ2A* and *PHF21A* (BHC20).

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Methods

We used whole transcriptome methodologies to measure total transcription in a number of biologic contexts involving Xist expression, endogenous or transgenic (forced), including transformed fibroblasts and human embryonic stem cells. We mined published mass spectrometric data to conduct proteomic analysis of Xist-interacting proteins that function as components of the Xist RNP complex. We used translational co-regulation methods which study patterns of gene expression across the transcriptome and across a multitude of cellular and biologic settings to decipher co-regulated gene products of a given query.